

Rajyoga Lifestyle: A Path to an Addiction-Free Life - A Questionnaire-Based Exploratory Thematic Study

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Abstract

The study aims to analyse how adopting a Rajyoga lifestyle as recommended by Brahma Kumaris contributes to addiction-free living among adults. Data was collected through an open-ended questionnaire distributed to 15 Rajyoga practitioners who before being associated with Brahma Kumaris, were under the influence of substance based or behavioral or digital addiction. The responses of the individuals were thematically analyzed to identify recurring patterns and opinions. The findings indicate that living a life-style i.e. waking early in the morning, having satvic i.e. pure diet, paying attention to own thoughts, words and deeds etc. as recommended by Brahma Kumaris along with regular practice of Rajyoga meditation fosters self-awareness, emotional balance, spiritual fulfillment, and self-attainment, which collectively improve self-control leading to reduced dependency on substances and habits. Participants highlighted gaining strength from the supreme source of energy through meditation, purity of lifestyle, and spiritual community support as key factors that help sustain an addiction-free life. The study concludes that adopting Rajyoga lifestyle can be an impactful, holistic, and self-empowering approach to overcoming addiction.

Keywords: Rajyoga, lifestyle, addiction, thematic study, spirituality, meditation

Introduction

Any type of addiction, substance-based or behavioral, has been a growing concern worldwide. Addiction often has its roots in the factors such as psychological stress, emotional dissatisfaction, lack of self-control, peer-pressure, as a sign of show-off etc. There is a positive correlation between substance usage and stress levels (Dr. Nagesh N V, 2023) [2]. Spiritual and meditative practices have now-a-days gained attention as alternative approaches to achieve emotional healing and freedom from dependency on such substance and behavior.

Leading a Rajyoga life-style that includes waking up early in the morning, doing amrit-wela meditation, daily listening of spiritual discourse, intermittent meditation practice through out the day, having satvic and pure diet etc. result in mental discipline and self-awareness. Rajyoga trains an individual in the art of controlling one's thoughts, emotions and actions through spiritual awareness. The inward journey of the self-promotes peace, clarity and emotional resilience that brings purity in thought, word, and action, encouraging individuals to live a stress free life with inner peace and

purpose rather than external stimulation. The present study is an attempt to explore how people who are leading the Rajyoga lifestyle experience its role in having a pure, calm and stress-free life, which ultimately leads to an addiction-free life.

Objectives of the Study

- To analyse the experiences of Rajyoga practitioners living a rajyoga life-style in maintaining an addiction-free routine.
- To identify important concepts and spiritual principles of Rajyoga that help in overcoming addictive habits.
- To analyze how Rajyoga lifestyle influences emotional and mental well-being.
- To have a thematic analysis on how spirituality supports addiction recovery.

Materials and Methods

Adopting an exploratory qualitative design, a semi-structured questionnaire with open-ended questions was administered to the participants. Thematic analysis was

done to interpret participants’ inputs.

The sample consisted of 15 adults (aged 25–60) Rajyoga practitioners selected through purposive sampling from Brahma Kumaris centers leading a Rajyoga lifestyle for at least one year. The selected individuals were trapped in substance based, behavioral or digital addiction before being associated with Brahma Kumaris and adopting a Rajyoga life-style.

Some of the questions included in questionnaire

1. How has Rajyoga meditation including the Rajyoga lifestyle influenced your habits or lifestyle?
2. Have you experienced any change in addictive tendencies after adopting Rajyoga life-style?
3. What aspects of Rajyoga practice (e.g., meditation, diet, company, knowledge) help you the most in remaining

addiction-free?

4. How has Rajyoga affected your emotional and mental stability?
5. What benefits from your life-experience would you tell other person struggling with addiction?

The questionnaire was distributed both physically and digitally (via Google Forms). Participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Responses were collected over a period of two weeks. All responses were read several times to gain familiarity, coded manually, and grouped into thematic categories.

Ethical Considerations

Participation was voluntary, with informed consent obtained. Anonymity and confidentiality were ensured.

Table 1: Findings and Thematic Analysis

S. No.	Theme	Response received from participants	Insight from the response
1.	Past Addictions	Some participants reported smoking and alcohol as addiction others reported about digital device addiction	All the respondents agreed that through leading Rajyoga lifestyle, they were able to have self-control which resulted in de-addiction.
2.	Changes in Daily Habits and Thoughts Pattern	All the respondents experienced positive attitude, discipline, self-awareness, peace of mind, stability, and greater self-satisfaction	Rajyoga and Rajyoga lifestyle inculcates discipline and mindfulness in daily life.
3.	Reduction in Cravings and Desires	Most of the respondents reported reduced anger, improved control over desires, and calmness.	Reduced emotional and behavioral sensitivity by adopting spiritual lifestyle and meditation
4.	Helpful Aspects of Rajyoga Lifestyle	Meditation, regular routine, early rising, healthy diet, and spiritual study were most cited	Structured spiritual lifestyle supports self-control, better handling of situation and de-addiction.
5.	Role of Spiritual Understanding	Participants agreed that the Connection with the Supreme Soul provides strength, peace, and inner stability	Communion with the Supreme source of energy fosters self-control and enhances resilience.
6.	Handling Temptation and Stress	Participants stated that they now remain calm and composed, handle stress positively, and avoid reactive behavior.	Practice of Rajyoga meditation enhances emotional regulation and coping skills
7.	Influence of Spiritual Environment	All the participants agreed that Rajyoga Center’s teachers, and group support played a major role in sustaining motivation and discipline.	Collective spiritual atmosphere together with right support and guidance reinforces positive habits.
8.	Advice for Others	All respondents suggested visiting Rajyoga centers, practicing meditation, and connecting with God for peace and self-control.	Rajyoga together with Rajyoga lifestyle is viewed as a practical and spiritual solution to addictions.

Discussion

Participants expressed that Rajyoga meditation enhanced their self-observation and helped them become conscious of harmful patterns. This awareness was stated to be the ‘first step toward freedom’ from addiction. Many practitioners described that regular meditation and spiritual study i.e. daily Murli fulfilled emotional needs that once led them toward addictive behaviours. Respondents reported reduced stress as well as anxiety and greater calmness, helping them resist urges and impulsive behaviour. Rajyoga encourages satvik diet, waking up early in the morning, positive thinking, and regular self-reflection - participants associated all of these facets with mental clarity, self-confidence and strong willpower. Many respondents appreciated the supportive community of Brahma Kumaris Rajyoga centers. The company of like-minded individuals reinforced positive habits. The themes highlight that the Rajyoga lifestyle provides both psychological and spiritual mechanisms and strength to overcome addiction. Meditation develops inner awareness and control over impulses. The satvik lifestyle supports purity of body and mind, while spiritual study along with interaction and support with Brahma Kumaris

community offer a sense of purpose and identity that replaces the emptiness often leading to addiction.

These findings align with prior research (Pandiamani & Murugesan, 2021; Nagendra, 2019) [4, 3] which shows that meditation-based approaches enhance self-regulation and reduce dependency behaviors. The spiritual aspect of Rajyoga, however, offers an additional dimension-connection with the Supreme-creating sustained motivation for purity and self-mastery.

Conclusion

This thematic study concludes that the Rajyoga lifestyle serves as a powerful path to living an addiction-free life. Through self-awareness, spiritual fulfillment, disciplined living, and community support, practitioners find holistic healing and freedom from dependency. Rajyoga not only aids in addiction recovery but also promotes long-term emotional and spiritual well-being limiting the chance to fall in the prey of addiction again. However, future research employing a bigger sample along with mixed methods-combining thematic and quantitative measures-may further substantiate these insights.

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